

Evaluation of Colour Change of Indicators. Specific Colour Discrimination of α -*o*-(Carboxyphenyl)-, α -*p*-(carboxyphenyl)-, α -*m*-(sulphophenyl)- and α -*p*-(sulphophenyl)azo-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide in Methanolic Sodium Methoxide and Ethanolic Sodium Ethoxide

V. A. JADHAV

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

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The sensitivity, pH's of maximum colour change and rapidity of colour change of α -*o*-(carboxyphenyl)-, α -*p*-(carboxyphenyl)-, α -*m*-(sulphophenyl)- and α -*p*-(sulphophenyl)azo-*p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (designated respectively as OCPNBC, PCPNBC, MSPNBC and PSPNBC), have been evaluated in methanolic sodium methoxide (MSM) and ethanolic sodium ethoxide (ESE) media which are calculated in terms of specific colour discrimination steps, pH_{mcc} and half-band width of changes of SCD in pH units. For rapid calculations of these values, the 1963 Commission International de L'Edairage (CIE) recommendation for perceptually – more uniform colour spacing – has been given preference to the Mac-Adams Ellipses and RUCS system. The chromatic separations calculated from coordinates obtained by these systems have been reported.

Specific colour discrimination (SCD) as a measure of sensitivity of colour change of an indicator was evaluated. In the present work, we have evaluated (SCD) for OCPNBC, PCPNBC, MSPNBC and SPNBC. (CIE) coordinates have been calculated in terms of (RUCS)¹ coordinates. Here, CIE and RUCS^{1,2} methods have been correlated.

Results and Discussion

From the experimental points, symmetrical peaks are plotted, showing two bands. From this, following values are measured :

- (i) pH values corresponding to peak height in pH_{mcc} , pH values at which there is maximum colour change³.
- (ii) Half-band of the curve pH-SCD, i.e. the pH at which values of SCD falls to half value at maximum colour change when such points are taken on ascending limb

Fig. 1.

and descending limb respectively, i.e. $[\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{L}}$ and $[\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{H}}$; the difference $[\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{H}} - [\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{L}} = \text{pH } 1/2\text{SCD}$. Fig. 1 gives symmetrical curves and $[\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{L}}$ and $[\text{pH SCD}]_{\text{H}}$ separated from pH_{mcc} (Table 1).

- (iii) In the above investigation, the solution was methanolic sodium methoxide and very clear solution at high pH⁴. The CIE coordinates *x-y* colour (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2.

points of four indicators have also been calculated. For RUCS system, *U-V* plots are shown in Fig. 3. The range of this indicator spread over four or three quadrants yellow, green and blue relation between specific colour discrimination is shown in Fig. 4. Fig.

TABLE I—COLOUR EVALUATION OF OHPNBC, MHPNBC, PHPNBC IN METHANOLIC SODIUM METHOXIDE AND ETHANOLIC SODIUM ETHOXIDE

Method	Indicator	pH _{Hcc}	pH _{Hcc}	pH _{mcc}	Separation of pH _{Hcc} - pH _{mcc}	Half-band width pH ₁ /2SCD = H.B.W.	Sensitivity = 1/SCD _{mcc}
<i>Methanolic sodium methoxide :</i>							
C.I.E.	OHPNBC	14.7	15.1	14.9	0.2	0.4	1/10.84 = 0.092
		16.2	17.3	16.75	0.55	1.1	1/24.7 = 0.040
	MHPNBC	14.10	14.70	14.40	0.30	0.30	1/16.50 = 0.061
		15.31	16.20	15.75	0.45	0.90	1/21.18 = 0.041
	PHPNBC	13.90	14.3	14.1	0.2	0.40	1/18.28 = 0.055
		15.30	16.1	15.7	0.4	0.8	1/28.40 = 0.035
RUCS	OHPNBC	14.80	15.3	15.05	0.25	0.5	1/14.42 = 0.069
		16.10	17.5	16.80	0.70	1.4	1/17.82 = 0.056
	MHPNBC	14.25	15.00	14.625	0.375	0.75	1/17.44 = 0.057
		15.15	16.13	15.65	0.50	1.00	1/16.08 = 0.062
	PHPNBC	13.90	14.45	14.175	0.275	0.55	1/22.60 = 0.044
		15.25	16.25	15.75	0.5	1.00	1/16.76 = 0.060
<i>Ethanolic sodium ethoxide :</i>							
C.I.E.	OCPNBC	13.55	14.50	14.025	0.475	0.95	1/6.16 = 0.162 330
		18.05	18.90	18.475	0.425	0.85	1/24.04 = 0.041 587
	PCPNBC	14.55	15.55	15.05	0.5	1.00	1/52.7 = 0.018 975
		16.50	17.00	16.75	0.25	0.5	1/12.21 = 0.081 900
	MSPNBC	16.05	16.50	16.275	0.225	0.45	1/26.66 = 0.399 040
		17.90	18.45	18.175	0.275	0.55	1/13.64 = 0.073 313
PSPNBC	15.45	15.90	15.675	0.225	0.45	1/16.33 = 0.061 236	
	16.95	17.35	17.15	0.20	0.40	1/31.93 = 0.031 318	
RUCS	OCPNBC	13.40	14.55	13.725	0.325	0.65	1/7.69 = 0.141 040
		18.05	18.95	18.50	0.45	0.90	1/22.52 = 0.044 404
	PCPNBC	14.55	15.25	14.90	0.35	0.70	1/8.58 = 0.116 550
		16.30	17.15	16.725	0.425	0.85	1/18.85 = 0.053 050
	MSPNBC	16.05	16.55	16.30	0.25	0.50	1/21.50 = 0.046 511
		18.00	18.55	18.30	0.25	0.50	1/16.15 = 0.061 919
PSPNBC	15.5	15.8	15.65	0.15	0.3	1/18.61 = 0.053 734	
	17.5	17.15	17.15	0.35	0.7	1/23.68 = 0.042 290	

5 presents plots of data as determined by Mac-Adams Ellipses.

(iv) From comparison of colour change well-known characteristics are confirmed. From C.I.E. system sensitivities of OCPNBC, PCPNBC, MSPNBC, PSPNBC in methanolic sodium methoxide and ethanolic sodium ethoxide media are (0.107, 0.033), (0.037, 0.030), (0.069, 0.044), (0.037, 0.041) pH and (0.041, 0.16), (0.01, 0.08), (0.061, 0.033) and (0.039, 0.07) units respectively, but in very high pH range indicators are not precipitated. The concentration of OCPNBC, PCPNBC were $1.6-10^{-5}$ M. The colour change intensity must be proportional to (H^M or H_2^M) (Table I).

Indicators must be available in pure, mono-ionic and dianionic forms and must be freely soluble in the solvents. All three forms must remain unaltered by light and stable towards strong alkali.

Experimental

Indicators were obtained by diazotising *o*-, *p*- (aminobenzoic acid) (10 mmol) with sodium nitrite (10

Fig. 3.

mmol) in an ice-bath. To it was added *p*-nitrobenzylcyanide (10 mmol) cooled in an ice-bath and then neutralised with 1 M NaOH. The resulting precipitates were dried, crystallised³ and purified chromatographically.

Similar procedure was used for indicators of OH groups which were obtained from amines containing SO₃H group. Metallic and sulphanic acid were diazotised and neutralised with NaOH. A 0.05% (w/v) solution of indicators was prepared in double-distilled methanol and ethanol. Sodium methoxide and sodium ethoxide were prepared by dissolving pure sodium metal (46 g) in double-distilled methanol/ethanol (2 dm³). Absorbance was measured on a Beckman DU-2 Spekol spectrophotometer using 10 mm glass cuvette and pH on a Radiometer 9404 pH-meter. Absorption spectrum of each indicator solution was taken at different pH's in 0.2 pH units steps.

From colour coordinates chromaticity differences was calculated by using C.I.E. distribution function for standard illuminant C₂. From the colour coordinates, the chromaticity difference was calculated as the number of standard deviation of colour matching on the basis of Mac-Adams Ellipses. The standard deviation (ds) was obtained from the equation,

$$\Delta s^2 = g_{11} dx^2 + 2g_{12} dx dy + g_{22} dy^2$$

where, dx and dy are the changes in x and y coordinates respectively, and g₁₁, 2g₁₂, g₂₂ are the values of constant ellipses corresponding to colour points.

As a unit colour step corresponds to 3 standard deviations of colour matching, Δc corresponding to the change of pH under consideration, could be calculated and compared. In order to evaluate quantitatively the sensitivity of various indicators at different pH's, the number of colour

Fig 4

discrimination steps for a small constant pH difference (say 0.1 pH unit) could be calculated. But this is difficult to achieve experimentally. Now more convenient procedure of calculating the average number of colour discrimination steps is for one pH unit. Rate of colour change is obtained experimentally for indicator between two close pH values.

We call this average number of colour discrimination step for one pH unit, the specific colour discrimination (SCD) which is obtained as

$$\frac{\Delta c}{\Delta pH} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta pH}$$

The (SCD) of each of indicators with change of pH is plotted in Fig. 4.

The corresponding coordinates U and V on the RUCS system, were calculated from the relations,

$$U = 0.075 - \frac{0.823(x + y - z)}{1x - 7.05336y - 1.64023}$$

$$V = \frac{3.6900x - 5.07713y - 1.36896}{1x - 7.05336y - 1.64023}$$

These are plotted in Fig. 3. In the present study, U and V should be considered as chromaticity coordinates on basis of RUCS system of Breckenridge and Schaub³.

The chromatic separations (Δσ) between respective points from the RUCS coordinates U, V were obtained from the relation,

$$\Delta \sigma = (U_2 - V_1)^2 + (V_2 - V_1)^2$$

In terms of standard deviation (Δs) of colour matching, which defines an area of shades of an individual hue indistinguishable from each other, Δo appears to be larger unit.

Fig 5

To evaluate Δσ in terms of ΔS, the ΔS/ΔpH values (Mac-Adams Ellipses method) were plotted against 1000 Δo/ΔpH for indicators (Fig. 5). The values of Δc/ΔpH for different indicators obtained by the RUCS system according to the equation,

$$\Delta c / \Delta pH = (1/2) \times (1000) \Delta o / \Delta pH$$

are shown in Fig. 5. The curves show the same pattern and nearly the same values as given in Fig. 1

A simplified transformation to the perceptually more uniform chromatic spacing has been recommended by the C.I.E.,

$$u = \frac{4x}{x + 15y + 36z}$$

$$v = \frac{6y}{x + 15y + 3z}$$

Calculations according to this recommendation have been done for the progress of colour change in the case of indicators.

References

1. V. M. BHUCHAR, V. P. KUKREJA and S. R. DAS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **43**, 1847.
2. D. L. MAC ADAM, *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1942, **32**, 267.
3. C. K. BHASKARE and A. J. MUKHEDKAR *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 667.
4. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH, Theory and Practice", New York, Wiley, 1964, p. 69.